

Innovative Teaching Approaches to attract, engage, and maintain women in STEM: W-STEM project

Dr. Francisco José García-Peñalvo

GRIAL Research Group
Computer Science Department

University of Salamanca, Spain

fgarcia@usal.es

<https://twitter.com/frangp>

Coimbra Group Seminar

*Innovation in Learning and Teaching in Science,
Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) fields*

Granada, Spain, 14 November 2019

UNIVERSIDAD
DE SALAMANCA
CAMPUS DE EXCELENCIA INTERNACIONAL

Outline

- Project information
- Consortium
- Objectives
- Target audience
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1. Project information

Building the future of Latin America: engaging women into STEM

Acronym

W-STEM

Funding body

**European Union. ERASMUS + Capacity-building in Higher Education
on Call for proposals EAC/AO5/2017**

Reference

598923-EPP-1-2018-1-ES-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP

Dates

3 years, 15/O1/2019 too 14/O1/2022

Budget

862.268€

Basic references

(García-Holgado et al., 2019a, 2019b; García-Peñalvo, 2019b, 2019c)

2. Consortium

2. Consortium

Associated Partner

External evaluator

Columbus

3. Objectives

- Improve strategies and mechanisms for attracting, accessing and guiding women in Latin America in STEM higher education programs
- W-STEM aims to guarantee the transformation of the current situation in Higher Education Institutions in Latin America

Photo by [Bradley Hook](https://www.pexels.com/photo/woman-wearing-vr-headset/) from [Pexels](https://www.pexels.com/photo/woman-wearing-vr-headset/)
<https://goo.gl/VbUxCx>

4. Target audience

Higher Education Institutions

STEM programs

Secondary schools

Girls and young women

5. Main actions

Measure the gender equality in enrolment and retention rates in STEM programs at undergraduate levels

Implement Universities' policies, strategies and organizational mechanisms for improving attraction, access and guidance at undergraduate levels in STEM programs

5. Main actions

Promote STEM studies vocation and choice in girls and young women in secondary schools as well as guidance in the first year of the STEM programs.

Develop an online training package for Higher Education Institutions to implement effective strategies to enhance attraction, access and guidance of Women in STEM programs

6. Results: self-assessment

Self-assessment questionnaire

- The aim is to know the situation of Latin American universities through indicators related to gender equality in STEM programs
- It has been applied in Europe in order to have valuable data to implement possible initiatives beyond the W-STEM project
- The self-assessment survey or matrix is based on the SAGA toolkit (UNESCO, 2017), a set of tools for monitoring and evaluating gender equality and integrating gender aspects into science, technology and innovation policies

Self-assessment questionnaire

- Indicators 4 to 26 have been taken from SAGA toolkit, introducing a small modification in indicator 9 "Total and proportion of women graduates of university programmes by field of study and educational level", leaving only the indicator according to the field of study
- Two indicators have been added
 - Indicator 46 in relation to the orientation of women enrolled and graduating from STEM programmes, based on SAGA indicator 9
 - Indicator 47 to measure female dropout in STEM programmes
- The instrument has been applied after the end of the 2018–2019 academic year in order to be able to work with the 2018 admission data

W-STEM institutional data collection survey																													
RAPPORTEUR's INFO																													
Firstname Lastname		Skype	E-mail	Mobile	Address	Zip	City	Country																					
ISCED-F 2013 variants		BROAD FIELD ->	05 Natural sciences, mathematics and statistics					06 Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs)			07 Engineering, manufacturing and construction				INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING	OTHER													
ISCED-F 2013 variants		NARROW FIELD ->	051 Biological and related sciences		052 Environment		053 Physical sciences		054 Mathematics and statistics		061 Information and Communication			071 Engineering and engineering trades															
ISCED-F 2013 variants		DETAILED FIELD ->	0511	0512	0521	0522	0531	0532	0533	0541	0542	0611	0612	0613	0711	0712	0713	0714	0715	0716	0721	0722	0723	0724	0731	0732			
			Biology	Biochemistry	Environmental sciences	Natural environments and wildlife	Chemistry	Earth sciences	Physics	Mathematics	Statistics	Computer use	Databases and network design and	Software and applications develop	Chemical engineering and processes	Environmental protection technology	Electricity and energy	Electronics and automation	Mechanics and metal trades	Motor vehicles, ships and aircraft	Food processing	Materials (glass, paper, plastic and	Textiles (clothes, footwear and leather)	Mining and extraction	Architecture and town planning	Building and civil engineering			
INSTITUTIONAL BACKGROUND INFO			COLUMN FOR TEXTUAL COMMENTS																										
INSTRUCTION: Please provide information on formal structures that could provide some insight on institutional purpose i.e. special activities and policies. These questions on programmes, staff and students will help us to understand the			WRITE YOUR ANSWER HERE																										
PROGRAMMES			INSTRUCTION: Mark all ISCED-F 2013 variants that you offer programmes																										
P.1. Which programmes / courses are you using for data collection, by field of study?			INSTRUCTION: If you do not have ISCED-F 2013 disaggregated data you may fill information to this column.																										
P.2. Do you have unique multidisciplinary STEM programmes that intend to attract especially female students?			WRITE YOUR ANSWER HERE																										
P.3. Length of programmes (years / months)			WRITE YOUR ANSWER HERE																										
4. STAFF			Teacher play an important role as models for students at all levels of education.																										
INSTRUCTION: Fill in the total and share of female staff by field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013):			INSTRUCTION: If you do not have ISCED-F 2013 disaggregated data you may fill information to this column.																										
4.1. Provide the total number of teaching staff members for first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018.																													
4.2. Provide the total number of female teaching staff members for first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018.																													
4.3. Provide the total number of staff trained on gender issues in education.																													
4.4. Provide the total number of female staff trained on gender equality issues in education.																													
Related policies:																													
4.5. What, if any, training on gender issues education does your university provide for its staff in STEM programmes?			WRITE YOUR ANSWER HERE																										
4.6. What, if any, benefits does your university provide for its staff advancing their gender competence?			WRITE YOUR ANSWER HERE																										
5. STUDENTS																													
INSTRUCTION: Fill in the total and share of female STUDENTS by field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013)			INSTRUCTION: If you do not have ISCED-F 2013 disaggregated data you may fill information to this column.																										
5.1. Provide the total number students by field of study in 2018 in your institution.																													
5.2. Provide the total number of female students by field of study in 2018.																													
6. ATTRACTION			How interested women are to apply to study in STEM programs?																										
INSTRUCTION: Fill in total and share of female applicants to university by field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013)			INSTRUCTION: If you do not have ISCED-F 2013 disaggregated data you may fill information to this column.																										
6.1. Provide the total number of applicants for first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018.																													
6.2. Provide the total number of female applicants for first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018.																													
Related policies:																													
6.3. What, if any, policies, processes and activities does your university implement as part of its attraction campaigns for			WRITE YOUR ANSWER HERE																										
6.4. What, if any, policies, processes and activities does your university implement as part of its attraction campaigns specifically for female applicants for STEM programmes?			WRITE YOUR ANSWER HERE																										

6. Results: mobile app

Flutter

6. Results: mobile app

Iñaki Tajés

Dr. Maria Biola Javierre Martínez, 2019 International Rising Talent (España). Biological Sciences, Molecular Biology, Genomics

Prof. Karen Hallberg, 2019 Laureate for Latin America (Argentina). Bariloche Atomic Center, CNEA/CONICET

Dr. María Molina, 2019 International Rising Talent (Argentina). Chemistry, Physical chemistry, Molecular biology

Dr. Ana Sofia Varela Gasque, 2019 International Rising Talent (México). Chemistry, Electrochemistry, Catalysis

6. Results: role models interviews

7. Website and social profiles

<https://wstemproject.eu>

wstemproject@gmail.com

Twitter

[@WSTEMProject](https://twitter.com/WSTEMProject)

Official hashtag

[#WSTEMproject](https://twitter.com/WSTEMProject)

Instagram

[@wstemproject](https://www.instagram.com/wstemproject)

Facebook

<https://www.facebook.com/wstemproject>

YouTube

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCS1EzRQqziO3AEYWSFMER_Q

8. Related projects

<http://www.taccle3.eu/>

[García-Peñalvo, 2016a, 2016b, 2017;
García-Peñalvo et al., 2016c, 2016d,
2018; García-Peñalvo & Mendes, 2018]

Virtual Alliances for Learning Society

<http://virtualalliances.eu/>

[García-Peñalvo et al., 2014a, 2014b,
2015a, 2015b, 2016a, 2016b]

**ROBOSTEAM - Integrating steam and
computational thinking development by
using robotics and physical devices**

<http://robosteamproject.eu/>

[Conde-González et al., 2019; Fernández-Llamas &
Conde-González, 2019; García-Peñalvo, 2019c; Gonçalves et al.,
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Recommended citation

García-Peñalvo, F.J. (2019). *Innovative Teaching Approaches to attract, engage, and maintain women in STEM: W-STEM project*. Coimbra Group Seminar. Innovation in Learning and Teaching in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) fields, 14 November 2019 – Granada, Spain. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3538939

Disclaimer

W-STEM (Building the future of Latin America: engaging women into STEM) is a project funded under European Union ERASMUS + Capacity-building in Higher Education Programme [598923-EPP-1-2018-1-ES-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP]

The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

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